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INSTITUTUL PENTRU STUDII POLITICE DE APĂRARE ȘI ISTORIE MILITARĂ

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Human Security in the new Strategic Concept of NATO: Linking Values and Practice

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ABSTRACT

Starting with 2019, NATO began developing its approach to human security which culminated in its inclusion in the new Strategic Concept adopted at the 2022 Madrid Summit. As expected, the document drew attention of the scientific community which devoted extensive analysis to it but neglected a central point of NATO's understanding of human security: the connection with NATO values and thus with liberal democracy as the political basis of the Alliance. This article addresses this gap by considering the contribution of human security to both the democratic resilience among NATO members and the strategic competition of the Alliance with authoritarian powers, as well as by analysing the reasons underpinning the emergence of NATO's interest in human security. It is thus possible to further a better understanding of the new Strategic Concept and avoid an incomplete reading of future NATO developments in the area of human security.

Keywords: human security, liberal democracy, 2022 Strategic Concept, democratic resilience, NATO values, authoritarian powers.

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Introduction

Human security emerged in 1994 as a concept capturing the priorities of the post-Cold War world¹ and it gradually gained priority at the United Nations where General Assembly decided on its common understanding in a landmark resolution adopted in 2012². Human security continues to be a relevant conceptual framework for the United Nations as proved by the report on this topic recently released by the UN Secretary General³. At the level of European Union, human security started to be thoughtfully considered with the publi-

cation in 2004 of the report *A Human Security Doctrine for Europe* (Barcelona Report)⁴ and the reflection process was consolidated by the release in 2009 of a subsequent report entitled *A European Way of Security* (Madrid Report)⁵. Human security was latter included in *A Global Strategy for the European Union's Foreign and Security Policy* (2016)⁶ and in *A Strategic Compass for Security and Defence* (2022)⁷. NATO started a serious discussion on its stance on human security in 2019 when a Human Security Unit began operating as part of the office of its Secretary General⁸. The same year, human security appeared for the

first time in a declaration following a meeting of heads of state and government, namely in the *London Declaration*⁹, and since then it is to be found in each final document adopted at NATO summits: *Brussels Summit Communiqué*¹⁰ (2021), *Madrid Summit Declaration*¹¹ (2022), and *Vilnius Summit Communiqué*¹² (2023). More importantly, the Strategic Concept adopted in 2022 at the Madrid Summit is the first such document to mention human security¹³.

By adopting an explicit human security approach, NATO follows the example of the United Nations and the European Union, thus opening new opportunities for cooperation with both organisations. The importance recently attached by NATO to human security provided the incentive for writing this article which critically examines the reception within the scientific community of NATO's perspective on human security and suggests a more elaborated reading of it that explores the relevance of NATO values for human security.

For this purpose, the first section is concerned with the underpinning values of liberal democracy as a basis shared by both NATO and human security, thus providing the overall direction of research. In the second section is conducted a literature review which considers, from the viewpoint of the connection between NATO values and human security, the new Strategic Concept; the methodological aspects of the paper are then built upon its findings. The third section refers to how documents relevant for the elaboration of the 2022 Strategic Concept connects human security and NATO values, and the final section presents the interplay between human security and NATO values as reflected in the new Strategic Concept and its associated documents.

1. Liberal democracy as a common denominator for NATO and human security

Values are an integral part of NATO, with the North Atlantic Treaty asserting in its pre-ambular section the prominence of democracy, individual liberty, and the rule of law. These values have been restated in the first two strategic concepts adopted by the Alliance during

the Cold War and included, in whole or in part, in the strategic concepts preceding the current one; the strategic concepts from 1991 and 1999 indicated as core values democracy, human rights and the rule of law, while the strategic concept from 2010 added individual liberty to them¹⁴. All four values mentioned in this latter document are included in the current Security Concept which also emphasises their paramount importance for the Alliance¹⁵.

As a result of being grounded on common liberal values¹⁶, NATO represented from the very beginning a community of values and this status was explicitly acknowledged in the 2010 Strategic Concept¹⁷. Functioning as a community, which could also be designated as a political community, NATO was always more than a collective defence alliance or a collective security alliance. Therefore it was able to generate and maintain for a long period or high degree of unity among its members and a strong public support for its objectives¹⁸. The values underpinning the creation of NATO expressed the attachment to Western democracy as opposed to the tyranny represented by the Soviet regime¹⁹, so that it could be rightly maintained, as recently the Minister for Foreign Affairs of Sweden did, that NATO is a defence community of Western democracies²⁰.

Liberal democracy²¹ is highly relevant not only for NATO, but also for human security. During the process of developing the latter concept within the United Nations, its relationship with democracy was clearly underlined. The Commission on Human Security, which played an instrumental role in this process, indicated in its report from 2003 that human security is best promoted by democratic states disposing of strong institutions and advancing the rule of law and the basic rights and freedoms of its people²². A few years later, in 2006, the International Institute for Democracy and Electoral Assistance equally acknowledged the relevance of democracy for human security, arguing that, for advancing human security, democracy should not be limited to electoral process and majority rule, but has to incorporate the rule of law and human rights²³. In a report from 2017, the Community of Democracies also connected democracy and human security, indicating that the type of de-

mocracy which best advances human security is liberal democracy, namely that which operates in a strong institutional framework, relies on competent bureaucracy, and enables the existence of the rule of law, human rights, and civil liberties²⁴.

Because liberal democracy is essential for the identity of NATO and equally an indispensable condition for people to enjoy human security to the fullest extent, the inclusion of human security in the 2022 NATO Strategic Concept, the first time when human security figures in such a high-profile document, is expected to be analysed in relevant literature from the viewpoint of both the relationship between human security and NATO values and, consequently, from the perspective of the contribution of human security to advancing liberal democracy. The next section explores this theoretical expectation and grounds on its findings the research methodology used in this paper.

2. NATO values-human security nexus in relevant literature on the 2022 Strategic Concept

An examination of relevant literature on the new Strategic Concept reveals that many authors who considered this document either did not address human security or mentioned it without establishing a connection with NATO values. Luis Tomé²⁵, Ming-hsien Wong²⁶, experts from the LSE IDEAS²⁷, Henrik Larsen, Rachel Ellehuus, Robin Allers, Johannes Gullestad Rø, Paul O'Neill, Christian Mölling, and Claudia Major²⁸, Alessandro Marrone²⁹, Stanley R. Sloan, Marcin Zaborowski³⁰, Gabriella Bolstad and Eskil Jakobsen³¹, Nikolaos Lampas and Constantinos Filis³² are examples of authors who make no reference to human security. The lack of any reference to human security was not anticipated because the introduction of human security in the new strategic concept represented a significant innovation. In the case of Tomé, Wong, Larsen, Ellehuus, Allers, Gullestad Rø, O'Neill, Mölling, Major, Gabriella Bolstad, and Eskil Jakobsen this absence it is even more evident given that they approach

the issues of NATO values and of threats to liberal democracy arising from both within the outside the Alliance.

Zoltan Szenes indicates the presence of human security in the new Strategic Concept but establishes no connection with NATO values and liberal democracy³³. Thierry Tardy acknowledges the existence of human security in this document and the prominence attributed therein to shared values, but he does not link the two topics³⁴. Bruno Tertrais limits himself to observe that human security appears in the Strategic Concept albeit he emphasises that this document draws attention on China as a power calling into question the values of the Alliance³⁵. Patrick Keller, despite noting that NATO supports an international order compatible with the democratic system shared by its members, only observes that human security is part of non-military responsibilities of NATO³⁶. Loïc Simonet, despite bringing to attention the centrality of NATO values as building blocks of liberal democracy and the danger posed to them by China, remarks solely the centrality of human security for crisis prevention and management and its significance for the cooperation between NATO and the European Union³⁷. Kaleigh Heard and Kristin Thue, who devote an entire commentary to the incorporation of human security in the new Strategic Concept, consider neither the interplay between NATO values and human security, nor the relevance of the former ones for this document³⁸.

In contrast with these latter authors, Tomas Valasek, in his capacity as acting general rapporteur for the Political Committee of NATO Parliamentary Assembly, brings together human security and liberal democracy in a report on the 2022 NATO Strategic Concept, but the way he associates them tends to be rather implicit³⁹. In a straightforward reading of this document, human security furthers liberal democracy in front of threats to it emerging from within the Alliance and from authoritarian competitors challenging the current rules-based international order. The expeditious manner in which this problem is presented together with the implicit way of approaching it hinders the understanding of how human security and NATO values are related in the 2022 Strategic Concept.

The literature review provides arguments in support of the idea that, when analysing the new Strategic Concept, the scientific community tends to overlook the deep and meaningful relationship between NATO values and human security, but that politicians closely associated with the activity of NATO are more likely to pay attention to this connection when considering the document. However, the examination of this issue at the level of NATO Parliamentary Assembly has an insufficient degree of analyticity and could pass quite unnoticed.

It follows that there is a gap in the relevant literature on the 2022 Strategic Concept and this paper aims at filling it by clearly and comprehensively presenting how liberal democracy and human security are related in this prominent document. Consequently, the research question guiding the article is the following one: What connection establishes the 2022 NATO Strategic Concept between NATO values/liberal democracy and human security and how this connection impacts the relevance for NATO of human security? From the methodological point of view, the research relies on document analysis and comparative analysis. The first method is used in relation with both NATO official documents and reports for the NATO Secretary General elaborated by independent experts. The second research method is applied to identify similarities and differences among documents leading up to the new Strategic Concept, between these documents and the new Strategic Concept, as well as between the latter and official NATO documents accompanying it.

To answer the research question, the following section examines documents relevant for the elaboration of the 2022 Strategic Concept.

3. Connection between liberal democracy and human security in the process leading up to the 2022 NATO Strategic Concept

When, back in December 2019, a NATO Leaders' Meeting was organized in London, the final document adopted at its conclusion, the *London Declaration*, put emphasis on common values and on the role of NATO as their

guarantor⁴⁰; it was also underlined the need to consolidate the political dimension of the Alliance⁴¹. Given that political cooperation refers to common values, the strengthening of the former was meant to advance the latter ones, and this interplay could operate as a framework for reading NATO stated preoccupation with increasing its involvement in the field of human security that was equally included in the declaration⁴². Under this interpretation, the development of an approach to human security served the purpose of consolidating the values upon which rested the Alliance as a political community. There was no direct connection in the *London Declaration* between human security and NATO values, but establishing it accords with the overall perspective put forward in this document. Determined to enable the Alliance to successfully adapt to new realities it was faced with, NATO leaders adopted the decision to initiate a process of reflection conducted by the Secretary General⁴³; obviously, this process necessarily included the issue of human security.

Jens Stoltenberg launched the reflection process in 2020 and, as part of it, he appointed on 31 March 2020 the members of the independent Reflection Group⁴⁴ and, later that year, established the NATO 2030 Young Leaders Group⁴⁵. The report of the first group, entitled *NATO 2030: United for a New Era*⁴⁶, was released in November 2020 and indicated that the issue of political cooperation goes beyond the military field and is embedded in the provisions of the North Atlantic Treaty committing the Alliance to its common values of democracy, individual liberty and the rule of law⁴⁷. According to this document, democracy was a traditional and highly important area of political cooperation and, in the current security context where main NATO rivals challenge democratic systems globally and within NATO, it needed to be clearly reaffirmed as a core value for the identity of the Alliance⁴⁸. It was argued that, just like during the Cold War era, democracy should be a key element differentiating NATO from its systemic competitors which promote authoritarianism⁴⁹. The Reflection Group expressed its concern about the NATO members ideological vulnerabilities and, in order to redress this problem,

it stressed the urgent need to establish a Centre of Excellence for Democratic Resilience⁵⁰. With respect to the means at the disposal of NATO for promoting democracy abroad, it was mentioned that the Alliance is no more favouring the export of democracy, but continued to prominently feature democracy in its partnership policy⁵¹. Considering that human security was about respect for human rights, the authors of the report included it under the scope of democracy which means that they supported the idea that liberal democracies were the best placed to provide human security. The association of human security with democracy was not designed to be exclusive of other values because democracy was understood as liberal democracy and, thus, as subsuming all NATO values. Taking into account the relevance for liberal democracy of human security, the report recommended NATO to give prominence to human security by mentioning it in strategic documents and specifying therein its relationship with the core tasks of the Alliance⁵²; human security would thus contribute to positively distinguish NATO from authoritarian states and terrorist organisations. Relying on how NATO had approached human security, the Reflection Group mentioned that it encompassed the provision of protection to civilians in armed conflicts, the countering of human trafficking, and both the prevention and response to sexual violence that is conflict-related⁵³; it was equally observed that NATO's practice indicated a growing willingness to integrate these elements into its operations.

The report by the NATO 2030 Young Leaders Group, named *NATO 2030: Embrace the change, guard the values*⁵⁴ and released in February 2021, also underlined the essential role that democracy, which has to be read herein as liberal democracy, had to play for NATO in the ongoing competition with authoritarian powers⁵⁵. It was recommended therefore that NATO strengthened its commitment to democracy and positioned itself in opposition with its main competitors as the leading worldwide promoter of democracy; export of democracy was not envisaged as a way of supporting democracy at international level, the power of own example and partner-

ships being preferred to instead⁵⁶. It was noted again that threats to democracy came not only from beyond the Alliance, but also from inside it so that it was indicated that NATO has to build democratic resilience. Human security was again linked with democracy, that has to be understood in this context as liberal democracy, and thus with the upholding of democracy among NATO members and internationally⁵⁷. NATO's involvement in the area of human security was equally conceived as a means to broaden the concept of security and, thus, to increase the importance it attributes to non-traditional security threats⁵⁸. It follows that the threats to democracy and, implicitly, to human security, were seen as belonging to the class of non-traditional threats affecting the security of NATO. To make human security effective, the report indicated that it should be turned into a military capability of NATO and that, to this end, threat analysis, operational planning and mission should refer to threats faced by people living in areas where NATO operates within the framework of deterrence and defence⁵⁹. Effectiveness of NATO's approach to human security also required that human security be incorporated in its doctrine and become part of educational and training programs offered by it.

At the NATO Brussels Summit from June 2021, it was approved the *NATO 2030* agenda put forward by Jens Stoltenberg⁶⁰. Albeit human security did not figure in his proposals, it was included therein the idea common to both reports that authoritarian states posed a security threat to the Alliance by affecting the value of democracy and, consequently, the rules-based international order supported by NATO.

In line with the mentioned reports and the *NATO 2030* agenda, the importance of values for the allies and the challenge to democracy posed by authoritarian powers competing with NATO became part of the *communiqué* adopted at the 2021 summit⁶¹. As in the two previous reports, human security is directly addressed and linked to all values upheld by NATO and, therefore, with liberal democracy; human security is thus conceived as instantiating the shared values of NATO. Unlike the report by NATO 2030 Young Leaders Group,

the *communiqué* did not confine human security to the task of deterrence and defence but clearly extends it beyond it to encompass all core tasks of the Alliance. NATO leaders also mentioned that the issues to be addressed by NATO within the framework of human security were protection of civilians in armed conflicts, prevention and response to conflict-related sexual violence, combatting trafficking of human beings, protection of children in armed conflict, and the protection of cultural property. The fact that human security covered more issues than those specified in the report of the Reflection Group indicated a tendency to broaden the scope of human security. There was agreement over the fact that incorporating human security into all these areas significantly contributed to NATO missions and operations being more effective.

The view of the Brussels Summit on the relationship between human security and NATO values was reflected in the *Secretary General's Annual Report 2021* so that human security was explicitly associated therein with these values and, consequently, with liberal democracy⁶². The annual report is even more explicit than the *communiqué* of the 2021 Brussels Summit when it comes to the relevance of values for human security, indicating that human security enables the application of values into missions, operations and activities undertaken by the Alliance⁶³. Human security is presented as a practical concept bridging the abstractness of values and the concreteness of NATO's actions with the effect that it functions as a conceptual framework for implementing values. According to the report of the Secretary General, human security became indispensable for realizing NATO values because NATO increasingly had to address threats to its security in civilian populated areas⁶⁴. It follows that human security considerations were seen to emerge out of practical operational necessities. Summing up, human security was conceived as an adequate instrument for giving effect to NATO's values in an operational environment that experienced significant changes.

It should be mentioned that the shadow strategic concept of NATO released in February 2022 by The Alphen Group, a document elaborated at its own initiative but addressed

to the Secretary General of the Alliance, recommended the link between human security and NATO values to be explicitly stated⁶⁵.

4. Human security and NATO values as related in the 2022 Strategic Concept and associated documents

Human security gained prominence at NATO level following the 2022 Madrid Summit where it was decided the inclusion of human security in the new strategic concept as an important concept with cross-cutting relevance within NATO. The common values of individual liberty, human rights, democracy and the rule of law prominently figure in this document which also stresses their high significance for the Alliance. However, the direct link between human security and NATO values is absent which represents a similarity with the 2019 *London Declaration*, but a salient difference compared with the reports of the Reflection Group and of the NATO 2030 Young Leaders Group, as well as with the 2021 *Brussels Summit communiqué* and the *Secretary General's Annual Report 2021*. However, human security could be said to be associated with the common allied values by the fact that it is included in all three core functions of NATO (deterrence and defence, crisis prevention and management, cooperative security) and these functions express and promote the respective values; it is to be remarked that crisis prevention and management is considered the core task for which human security plays a central part⁶⁶.

The 2022 Strategic Concept takes over from the reports leading up to the *NATO 2030* agenda, and from the *communiqué* adopted at the 2021 NATO Summit, the idea that NATO is involved in a strategic competition which negatively impacts the values shared by its members and the idea that, in the particular case of democracy, understood as liberal democracy, this competition is detrimental to it because rival authoritarian powers act to undermine the democratic process of NATO members and to reduce the spread of democracy worldwide. The countering of threats to democracy by consolidating it among NATO

members and promoting it through enlargement and partnership policies is also taken from previous documents. The direct link between human security and NATO values is equally missing from the declaration of the 2022 Madrid Summit which restates from the Strategic Concept that human security is a primary topic and belongs to each core task assumed by the Alliance⁶⁷.

Building on the importance attributed to human security in the new Strategic Concept, NATO developed its approach on human security by adopting at the 2022 Madrid Summit the *Human Security. Approach and Guiding Principles*⁶⁸. Unlike the strategic concept, this document, which closely pairs with it, explicitly associates human security with all NATO values and indicates that human security provides applicability to these values in the context of NATO involvement in situations of conflict and crisis, being thus a valuable tool for NATO⁶⁹. The adoption of the *Human Security. Approach and Guiding Principles* at the same time with the Strategic Concept could indicate that the later did not insist on the relationship between human security and NATO values precisely because this was done in the former document. Similar to previous documents, NATO's approach and guiding principles on human security indicate that human security increases the effectiveness of NATO missions and operations, but adds that this positive effect resulted from human security making possible a better understanding of conflicts and crisis by focusing on their human aspects. The document under consideration broadens the justification, provided in the *Secretary General's Annual Report 2021*, for the need to embrace human security indicating not only that the Alliance is forced to take action in areas with civilian population, but also that current conflicts, as plainly proven by the practices of the Russian Federation in its war against Ukraine, deliberately victimise civilians and put them at risk for advancing military objectives. The five distinct areas that, according to the decisions reached at the 2021 NATO Summit, are encompassed by human security, figure in their entirety in the *Human Security. Approach and Guiding Principles* and, in line with the Strategic Concept, are said to be incorporated in all core tasks of the Alliance.

NATO gave further effect to the implementation of human security by including under its scope specific policies designed for four areas that it covered⁷⁰, and a policy for the protection of cultural property is in the process of being drawn up⁷¹. The existing such policies clearly state that human security and NATO values are interconnected in view of the latter being translated into practice.

Conclusions

During the process that led to the adoption of the new Strategic Concept, human security was directly linked with NATO values understood as constitutive elements of liberal democracy. The association figured in documents elaborated outside the institutional framework of the Alliance (the report by the Independent Group, the report by the NATO 2030 Young Leaders Group, the report by Alphen Group) and within that framework (2021 *Brussels Summit Communiqué* and the *Secretary General's Annual Report 2021*), but was missing from the *London Declaration* that initiated the process which resulted in the present strategic concept of the Alliance. The strategic concept currently in force and the 2022 *Madrid Summit Declaration* did not explicitly connect human security and NATO values, while the *Human Security. Approach and Guiding Principles* agreed upon at 2022 Madrid Summit, as well as all NATO policies for implementing areas of human security, have made this relationship apparent. It is tempting to explain the neglect of this relationship in the literature on the 2022 Strategic Concept as a result of its absence from this document and from the 2022 *Madrid Summit Declaration*. However, the general validity of this explanation is questionable given that there are authors – e.g. Thierry Tardy, Bruno Tertrais, Patrick Keller, Zoltan Szenes, Loïc Simonet - who referred to the independent reports preceding the adoption of the 2022 Strategic Concept and/or to the 2021 *Brussels Summit Communiqué*, documents where human security is explicitly put in relation to NATO values.

The lack of attention for the human security-NATO values nexus hampers understand-

ing of the reasons underpinning its rise to prominence within NATO and, consequently, of its relevance for the Alliance. By paying attention to this relationship, human security could be seen as a tool for implementing NATO values in its missions and operations because the operational environment increasingly challenges these values as a result of deliberate victimisation of civilians in armed conflicts and of the need for military operations to be conducted in civilian populated areas; from this perspective, the war in Ukraine, where the Russian Federation targets civilians on a large scale, reveals itself as a driving factor for NATO's engagement with human security. As a community of liberal democracies, NATO can only live up to its defining values and give due consideration to civilians at risk in areas under its responsibility. Consideration of the interplay between NATO values and human security equally enables one to acknowledge that human security is an important tool in the Cold-War reminiscent worldwide ideological confrontation with authoritarian powers that NATO is involved in for safeguarding liberal democracy. Moreover, paying due attention to the connection between human security and NATO values highlights that a human security approach contributes to building democratic resilience among NATO members. Highlighting NATO value-driven concern for human security makes possible to observe that the embedment of the concern for the condition of civilians affected by NATO missions and operations is also motivated by the pragmatic reason not to impede their success in terms of creating conditions for long-term peace and security.

Without a clear view on how human security and NATO values are related, further developments in NATO's approach to human security will not be adequately understood within the scientific community and this will entail detrimental consequences for the reception by scholars of NATO's achievements in this field. Furthermore, emphasising the close relationship existing between liberal democracy and human security is highly relevant at a moment when NATO Secretary General warns against the ongoing strengthening of an alliance among authoritarian powers that brings together Russian Federation, China, Iran, and North Korea⁷².

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¹⁶ Nathalie Durhin, *NATO and its founding values: renewal of vows or "conscious uncoupling"?* p. 7, 1 September 2020, pp. 5-14, https://www.jstor.org/stable/pdf/resrep26057.6.pdf?refreqid=fastly-default%3A54d58636066aaf45ef0150ebab2bealc&ab_segments=&origin=&initiator=&acceptTC=1, 05.02.2024.

¹⁷ *Active Engagement, Modern Defence*, paragraph 2.

¹⁸ Nathalie Durhin, *op. cit.*, pp. 5, 6, Luis Tomé, *NATO as a community of values and its new political role*, *Atlantisch Perspectief*, 2022, Vol. 46, No. 4, pp. 24-2, <https://www.atlcom.nl/artikel-atlantisch-perspectief/natos-new-strategic-concept-our-blueprint-for-navigating-a-more-dangerous-and-competitive-world-2/>, 15.02.2024, Gunter Rinsche, *NATO as a Community of Values. Manfred Wörner Memorial Lecture*, 2 June 1999, https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/opinions_27550.htm?selectedLocale=en, 09.03.2024.

¹⁹ Raymond Aaron, *La communauté atlantique: 1949-1982*, *Politique étrangère*, Vol.48, 1983/4, pp.827-839, https://www.ifri.org/sites/default/files/atoms/files/la_communaute_atlantique_-_1949-1982_article.pdf, 14.02.2024. According to Aaron, the civilizational community existing among NATO members is less relevant for the success of the Alliance than the political community it represents. His argument is based on the historical fact that the former type of community is by no means a condition for peaceful coexistence as plainly proved by the countless wars between Western European states.

²⁰ Government Offices of Sweden, *Statement of Government Policy Following Sweden's Accession to NATO*, 20 March 2024, <https://www.government.se/speeches/2024/03/statement-of-government-policy-following-swedens-accession-to-nato/>, 19.03.2024.

²¹ The liberal democracy could be said to be a sophisticated form of democracy (See Ted Piccone, *Democracy and human security. Policy brief*, September 2017, pp. 2 https://www.brookings.edu/wpcontent/uploads/2017/08/fp_20170905_democracy_human_security.pdf, 14.03.2024). On the interplay between liberal democracy and the rule of law, individual liberty, and human

rights see Vasileios Adamidis, *Democracy, populism, and the rule of law: A reconsideration of their interconnectedness*, p. 4, *Politics*, 2021, <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/02633957211041444>, 09.03.2024, Wouter van der Brug, Sebastian Adrian Popa, Sara B Hobolt, Hermann Schmitt, *Illiberal democratic attitudes and support for the EU*, p. 540, *Politics* 2021, Vol. 41(4) 537–561, <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0263395720975970>, 10.03.2024, Fareed Zakaria, *The Rise of Illiberal Democracy*, *Foreign Affairs*, p. 22, vol. 76, no. 6, 1997, pp. 22-43. Liberal democracy is usually contrasted with illiberal democracy on grounds that the latter is incompatible with the rule of law, individual liberty, and human rights.

²² Commission on Human Security, *Human Security Now: Protecting and Empowering People*, 2003, pp. 68,133, <https://reliefweb.int/report/world/human-security-now-protecting-and-empowering-people>, 12.01.2024.

²³ International Institute for Democracy and Electoral Assistance, *Democracy, Conflict and Human Security. Policy Summary: Key Findings and Recommendations*, Stockholm, 2006, pp. 6, 7, 11, <https://www.idea.int/sites/default/files/publications/chapters/democracy-conflict-and-human-security/democracy-conflict-and-human-security-handbook-policy-summary.pdf>, 16.01.2024.

²⁴ Community of Democracies, *Liberal Democracy and the Path to Peace and Security. A Report of Community of Democracies*, September 2017, pp. 8, 9, 15 https://www.brookings.edu/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/fp_20170912_liberal_democracy_peace_security.pdf, 23.12.2023.

²⁵ Luis Tomé, *op. cit.*

²⁶ Ming-hsien Wong, *NATO's 2022 Strategic Concept and Its Impact on Global Security*, *Taiwan Strategists* No. 15, 2022, pp. 1-21, <https://www.pf.org.tw/en/pfen/38-9747.html>, 13.01.2024.

²⁷ LSE IDEAS, *NATO's 2022 Strategic Concept: One Year On*. Strategic Update, September 2023, <https://www2.lse.ac.uk/ideas/Assets/Documents/updates/2023-SU-NATO-OneYearOn.pdf>, 22.12.2023. The publication summarizes the outcomes of a roundtable attended by General Sir James Everard, Stuart Austin, Professor Gordon Barrass, Professor Christopher Coker, Tom McKane, Hugh Sandeman, Susan Scholefield, and Peter Watkins.

²⁸ Rachel Ellehuus, Robin Allers, Johannes Gullestad Rø, Paul O'Neill, Dr. Christian Mölling, Dr. Claudia Major, *NATO's 2030 Reflection Process and the New Strategic Concept Views from Berlin, London, Oslo, and Washington*, DGAP Report, No. 03 January 2022, <https://dgap.org/en/research/publications/natos-2030-reflection-process-and-new-strategic-concept>, 12.01.2024.

²⁹ Alessandro Marrone, *NATO's New Strategic Concept: Novelties and Priorities*, *Commentaries* 22|30, July 2022, <https://www.iai.it/sites/default/files/iaicom2230.pdf>, 12.01.2024.

³⁰ Marcin Zaborowski, *NATO Strategic Concept in the shadow of the war in Thierry Tardy (ed.), NATO's New Strategic Concept*, NDC RESEARCH PAPER No. 25, September 2022, <https://www.ndc.nato.int/news/news.php?icode=1737>, 17.02.2024.

³¹ Gabriella Bolstad, Eskil Jakobsen, *NATO's 2022 Strategic Concept Change, Continuity and Implications*,

Policy Brief, 5 / 2022, <https://www.nupi.no/en/news/nato-s-2022-strategic-concept-change-continuity-and-implications>, 16.03.2024.

³² Nikolaos Lampas, Constantinos Filis, *NATO's strategic concept: Implications for Greece and Türkiye*, Security and Defence Quarterly, Vol. 44, No. 4, pp. 38–54, https://securityanddefence.pl/pdf-174813-97094?filename=NATOs%20Strategic%20Concept_.pdf, 21.02.2024.

³³ Zoltan Szenes, *Reinforcing Deterrence: Assessing NATO's 2022 Strategic Concept*, Defense & Security Analysis, 39:4, 2023, pp. 539–560, <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/14751798.2023.2270230>, 12.03.2024.

³⁴ Thierry Tardy, *Introduction*, p. 3 in Thierry Tardy (ed.), *op. cit.* and Thierry Tardy, *Six takeaways from NATO's new Strategic Concept*, p. 15 in Thierry Tardy (ed.), *op. cit.* With respect to human security, he only indicates that it belongs to the class of soft security issues, is an area of NATO-EU cooperation, and has a relatively low visibility in the Strategic Concept.

³⁵ Bruno Tertrais, *An evolutionary, not revolutionary, Strategic Concept*, p. 28, in Thierry Tardy (ed.), *op. cit.*

³⁶ Patrick Keller, *The new status quo concept*, p. 36 in Thierry Tardy (ed.), *op. cit.*

³⁷ Loic Simonet, *NATO's 2022 Strategic Concept: Analysis and implications for Austria*, Working Paper 115, pp. 7, 9, 13, Austrian Institute for International Affairs, 2023, <https://www.oii.ac.at/cms/media/working-paper-115-natos-2022-strategic-concept.pdf>, 05.02.2024.

³⁸ Kaleigh Heard, Kristin Thue, *A New Era? NATO's Prioritization of Human Security in an Insecure World*, 10 August 2022, <https://www.rand.org/pubs/commentary/2022/08/a-new-era-natos-prioritisation-of-human-security-in.html>, 12.03.2024.

³⁹ Tomas Valasek, Political Committee of NATO Parliamentary Assembly, *NATO's Political and Security Adaptation in Response to Russia's War: Assessing the New Strategic Concept and Implementation of the Madrid Summit Decisions*, pp. 15, 16, General Report, 19 November 2022, <https://www.nato-pa.int/document/2022-natos-political-and-security-adaptation-response-russias-war-rethinking-strategic>, 14.02.2024. Here is the paragraph introducing human security “The new Strategic Concept has taken seriously the calls to reaffirm NATO's democratic credentials. The Allies have not only reiterated commitment to common values of individual liberty, human rights, democracy and the rule of law, but also clearly identified authoritarian actors as a threat to NATO's interests and values. These actors interfere in democratic processes in Allied countries and make “a deliberate effort to undermine multilateral norms and institutions”. It is significant that NATO is identified as “a bulwark of the rules-based international order”, and Allies pledged to “stand up for our shared values and the rules-based international order”. As noted, the cooperative security section prioritizes partnerships with those nations that share NATO's values. *There are also numerous references to human security throughout the text, including the commitment to the protection of civilians as central to NATO's approach to crisis prevention and management. The Strategic Concept highlights the importance of the Women, Peace and Security agenda across all NATO core tasks* [emphasis added].”

⁴⁰ *London Declaration*, paragraphs 1, 9.

⁴¹ *Ibidem*, paragraph 7.

⁴² *Ibidem*, paragraph 6.

⁴³ *Ibidem*, paragraph 7.

⁴⁴ NATO, Reflection Group, <https://www.nato.int/nato2030/independent-group/>, 13.03.2024.

⁴⁵ NATO, NATO 2030 Young Leaders Group, <https://www.nato.int/nato2030/young-leaders/>, 13.03.2024.

⁴⁶ Reflection Group, *NATO 2030: United for a New Era. Analysis and Recommendations of the Reflection Group Appointed by the NATO Secretary General*, 25 November 2020, https://www.nato.int/nato_static_fl2014/assets/pdf/2020/12/pdf/201201-Reflection-Group-Final-Report-Uni.pdf, 06.03.2024.

⁴⁷ *Ibidem*, p. 20.

⁴⁸ *Ibidem*, pp. 10, 14, 20.

⁴⁹ *Ibidem*, p. 51.

⁵⁰ *Ibidem*, pp. 5, 14.

⁵¹ *Ibidem*, pp. 20, 57.

⁵² *Ibidem*, p. 43.

⁵³ *Ibidem*, p. 43.

⁵⁴ NATO 2030 Young Leaders Group, *NATO 2030: Embrace the change, guard the values. A report by the NATO 2030 Young Leaders Group – for this generation and the next*, 4 February 2021, https://www.nato.int/nato_static_fl2014/assets/pdf/2021/2/pdf/210204-NATO2030-YoungLeadersReport.pdf, 13.03.2024.

⁵⁵ *Ibidem*, p. 4. Rule of law and individual liberty are also mentioned but the focus on the value of democracy is justified, as in the case of the report of the Reflection Group, by its broad meaning (liberal democracy) that encompasses the other two values (see p. 10).

⁵⁶ *Ibidem*, pp. 10, 12.

⁵⁷ *Ibidem*, p. 11.

⁵⁸ *Ibidem*, p. 3.

⁵⁹ *Ibidem*, p. 7. Human security as a military capability is discussed in the first part of the report bearing the title of *A 360° defence and deterrence for a resilient Euro-Atlantic space*, a positioning which indicates that human security relates only with this core task of NATO.

⁶⁰ NATO, *NATO 2030. Factsheet*, June 2021, https://www.nato.int/nato_static_fl2014/assets/pdf/2021/6/pdf/2106-factsheet-nato2030-en.pdf, 17.02.2024.

⁶¹ NATO, *Brussels Summit Communiqué. Issued by the Heads of State and Government participating in the meeting of the North Atlantic Council in Brussels 14 June 2021*, paragraphs 2, 3.

⁶² NATO, *The Secretary General's Annual Report 2021*, 31 March 2022, p. 90. https://www.nato.int/nato_static_fl2014/assets/pdf/2022/3/pdf/sgar21-en.pdf, 04.03.2024.

⁶³ *Ibidem*, pp. 82, 90.

⁶⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 90.

⁶⁵ Alphen Group (TAG), *The TAG NATO Shadow Strategic Concept 2022: Preserving Peace, Protecting People. A report by the Alphen Group (TAG) for the Secretary General on the 2022 NATO Strategic Concept*, February 2022, <https://www.gmfus.org/sites/default/files/2022-02/TAG%20-%20NATO%20Strategic%20Concept%20-%20NONPRINT.pdf>, 18.03.2024. “Taking a human-security approach is a reflection of Alliance values and makes NATO more operationally effective” (paragraph 54).

⁶⁶ NATO 2022 *Strategic Concept*, paragraph 5.

⁶⁷ *Madrid Summit Declaration. Issued by NATO Heads of State and Government participating in the meeting of the North Atlantic Council in Madrid 29 June 2022*, paragraph 13.

⁶⁸ NATO, *Approach and Guiding Principles*, 14 October 2022, https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/official_texts_208515.htm?selectedLocale=en, 12.02.2024.

⁶⁹ *Ibidem*, paragraph 3. “The notion of human security directly links NATO’s common values of individual liberty, human rights, democracy and the rule of law to NATO practice”.

⁷⁰ NATO, *Human security*, 20 July 2023, https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_181779.htm#children, 22.03.2024.

⁷¹ In February 2023, NATO indicated that the process of drafting a strategy for cultural property protection was going to be initiated (NATO, *NATO hosts conference on Cultural Property Protection*, 9 February 2023, https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/news_211795.htm, 21.02.2024).

⁷² *Laura Kuenssberg: West facing ‘authoritarian’ alliance, says NATO chief*, 06.04.2024, <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-politics-68743805>, 09.04.2024.